

THE EXPERIENCE OF FOREIGN COUNTRIES IN THE ELIMINATION OF PEDAGOGICAL CONFLICTS

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Abstract. *The article describes the conflicts that occur in the pedagogical activity of the teacher, their types, causes, and procedures for resolving them. In addition, there are ideas about the pedagogical and psychological features of pedagogical conflicts, and thus ways to prevent professional deformation.*

Keywords: *conflict, administrative conflict, pedagogical conflict, optimization, globalization, motivational conflict, moral conflict.*

Today, along with developments, updates, changes and technological processes in every field, the use of new technologies and Internet resources is increasing in the educational system. Nowadays, students learn independently through various sources can get and learn. He has the opportunity to get some knowledge from his parents or tutor. Even if the teacher does not know the subject well, he learns a part of it and compares the knowledge given by the teacher on this subject. If the teacher gives shallow knowledge or wrong information, the student will lose respect for the teacher. Of course, he brags about it to his classmates. This generally leads to not listening to the lesson and disrespecting the subject, and eventually losing the desire to master the subject. The result, the teacher and the student conflicts of various forms arise between them. The frequent repetition of such a situation causes the teacher's attitude to his profession to fade, and a professional deformation situation is observed in the teacher. Therefore, in pedagogic-psychological research, to prevent conflicts in pedagogical activity, their elimination remains an urgent problem.

The practical actions of the pedagogue as a specialist in the search for measures to prevent and eliminate negative pedagogical conflicts represent his work on himself. The teacher of the students as a leader, he should ensure the full performance of his creative tasks in educational institutions and form pedagogical orientation. Conflict is one of the important events in the pedagogical process is counted.

Conflict is a clash of opposing, incompatible forces, a lack of mutual agreement between two or more parties, a conflict representing a conflict of interests [1.46].

Pedagogical conflict is a teacher and student, teacher and parents.

It is a conflict of interest, mutual opposition, argument and conflict between colleagues and management in the pedagogical process.

A teacher should be well-educated, intellectually, morally, spiritually mature, have a wide range of knowledge, speak fluently, and possess pedagogical skills. Pedagogical skills of the teacher are evident mainly in classroom and auditorium activities. The teacher and the student should have a lively language, get ideas, be sincere, respect each other, and work together to achieve the main goal.

Pedagogical conflicts give impetus to the appearance of professional deformation in the teacher's activity. Conflicts that do not find a positive solution on a regular basis can cause stress, mental tension, and emotional burnout syndrome in the teacher's personality.

Pedagogical conflict has a number of signs. Its main characteristics are as follows:

- Crisis;
- Misunderstanding;
- An unexpected event;
- Tension;
- Inconvenience;
- Internal and external anxiety;
- Fear that is difficult to overcome.

Factors causing pedagogical conflicts are:

- Information factor;
- Attitude factor;
- Behavioral factor.

Czech pedagogue Ya. A. Komensky defines "teaching profession as a proud profession that is higher than any other profession on earth." According to A. Navoi, "...sometimes one person is unable to educate one child. The teacher is a group of children teaches" in his works. In this process, the teacher suffers a lot and experiences hardships. Therefore, students should feel that they are indebted to the teacher for life.

Pedagogical conflict from a psychological point of view, the sciences of pedagogy and psychology are inextricably linked. Both of them study one common process - human mental activity and behavior. A modern teacher cannot be a social psychologist. Therefore, it is necessary to be able to establish mutual relations between students, to know how to use pedagogical and psychological mechanisms in the children's group. The environment in which he lives, the role of society is very important in the formation of personality.

The main types of pedagogical conflicts:

- Internal personal conflict;
- Motivational conflict. Unimplemented activity conflict.
- Ethical conflict. Interpersonal and intergroup conflicts.

According to the duration, pedagogical conflicts are divided into several types.

Their main types are:

- Disputes that end in a short period of time;
- Weak, sluggish conflicts;
- Long-term disputes;
- Strong, fast conflicts.

Another factor that causes conflicts is living the condition is not good. If the teacher is under stress, he may behave unfairly towards the student and make the above mistakes unknowingly. If the student has a bad lifestyle, not only the teacher but also everyone around him will have a conflicting situation and severe psychological problems a process condition may occur.

Moral conflict - morality is one of the forms of social consciousness, it can be seen in the system of certain regulated behavior that people living in a certain society act on, to each other, to society, to public property, to the family, to the means of production.

In order to prevent conflicts between teachers and students, the teacher should be able to prevent conflicts. Our modern way of conflict management, correct resolution of conflicting relationships we have to find.

A number of methods are used to resolve pedagogical conflicts.

Among them, the most effective ways are:

- Not expanding the scope of the conflict.
- Offer convenient solutions.
- Do not apply, do not use prohibited methods.
- Reducing the number of complaints.
- To deal with secondary issues in an integrated manner.
- Derogatory words of the subjects involved in the conflict not to use

A number of methods are also used to resolve pedagogical conflicts. Among them, we can list the following from the most effective methods: One of the important events in the pedagogical process is a conflict, and in the situations when they arise, they lead to monopoly in social relations Usually pedagogical conflicts are two ways [4.98]:

- Pedagogical method
- It is divided into types of resolution by administrative method.

The teacher's image is about his personality to others while imparting "information" has an effective impact on students. Therefore, the teacher's image should reflect simplicity, orderliness, and neatness.

Pedagogical methods of conflict resolution:

- Conversation.
- Make a request.
- Persuasion.
- Clarification of the requirements imposed on the participants in the conflict and the wrongness of the participants' behavior.

Administrative methods of dispute resolution:

- Suppressing the interests of parties to the conflict by force;
- Transfer them to another job;
- Separation of conflict participants in various ways;
- Decision of the Ethics Commission;
- Leader's order;
- Court decision.

It is necessary for the teacher to be able to provide pedagogical, psychological and pedagogical support to the participants of the pedagogical dispute.

Types of pedagogical and psychological assistance provided to subjects of pedagogical conflict:

- Giving advice;
- Provision of informational support;
- Diagnosis;
- Organization of practical trainings;

In conclusion, by studying and analyzing the pedagogical-psychological characteristics of conflicts that arise in the teacher's pedagogical activity, finding their comprehensive ways and

applying them in practice, eliminating conflicts prevents the occurrence of professional deformations helps to get.

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